

Comparative Evaluation of Remaining Pericervical Dentin Thickness after Instrumentation with Different Rotary File Systems with and Without Coronal Flaring Using CBCT: An in Vitro Study

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Preservation of pericervical dentin (PCD) is a fundamental determinant of the biomechanical integrity and long-term prognosis of endodontically treated teeth. Excessive dentin removal during instrumentation, particularly in the cervical region, may predispose teeth to structural failure. Contemporary rotary systems are designed to optimize canal shaping while minimizing dentin loss; however, variations exist among different file systems and preparation techniques. **Aim:** This study aimed to evaluate and compare the remaining pericervical dentin thickness following instrumentation with different rotary file systems, with and without coronal flaring, using cone beam computed tomography (CBCT). **Methods:** Sixty extracted human mandibular first molars were selected and standardized. Samples were randomly divided into two groups: with coronal flaring and without coronal flaring (n = 30 each). Each group was further subdivided based on instrumentation system: TruNatomy, ProTaper Gold, and K3XF (n = 10 each). Pre- and post-instrumentation CBCT scans were obtained. Measurements of dentin thickness were recorded at 1 mm, 2 mm, 3 mm, and 4 mm below the furcation. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, Tukey post hoc tests, and independent t-tests. **Study Design:** In vitro comparative CBCT study. **Results:** TruNatomy consistently demonstrated the highest remaining dentin thickness at all levels, followed by K3XF and ProTaper Gold. Differences among file systems were statistically significant (p < 0.001). Coronal flaring resulted in slightly reduced dentin thickness; however, these differences were not statistically significant (p > 0.05). **Conclusion:** Rotary file design significantly influences pericervical dentin preservation. TruNatomy exhibited superior conservative shaping ability. Coronal flaring, when performed judiciously, does not significantly compromise dentin thickness.

Keywords: *Pericervical dentin, Cone beam computed tomography, TruNatomy, ProTaper Gold, K3XF, minimally invasive endodontics, coronal flaring, rotary instrumentation*

INTRODUCTION:

Endodontic therapy is fundamentally directed toward the elimination of infection within the root canal system and the prevention of reinfection. This objective is achieved through a combination of biomechanical preparation, chemical disinfection, and three-dimensional obturation. Among these steps, cleaning and shaping of the root canal system play a pivotal role, as they directly influence the efficacy of microbial reduction and the quality of the final seal.

While adequate canal preparation is essential for successful treatment, it must be performed with careful consideration of the structural integrity of the tooth. Excessive removal of dentin during instrumentation has been associated with reduced fracture resistance and an increased risk of catastrophic failure in endodontically treated teeth. In this context, the concept of dentin preservation has gained considerable importance in contemporary endodontics.

Pericervical dentin (PCD), defined as the dentin extending approximately 4 mm coronal and apical to the

crestal bone, is recognized as a critical structural zone. This region plays a key role in the distribution of occlusal stresses from the crown to the root. Loss of dentin in this area significantly compromises the biomechanical behavior of the tooth, predisposing it to vertical root fractures. The importance of preserving PCD is particularly evident in mandibular molars, where the mesial roots often exhibit thin dentinal walls and are susceptible to procedural errors such as strip perforation. Coronal flaring is an integral component of root canal preparation. It facilitates straight-line access to the apical region, enhances the penetration and effectiveness of irrigants, and reduces torsional stress on rotary instruments. Despite these advantages, aggressive coronal enlargement may result in unnecessary removal of dentin in the cervical region, thereby weakening the tooth structure. This creates a clinical dilemma between achieving adequate canal shaping and preserving dentin. Mandibular molars are particularly susceptible to excessive dentin removal because of the presence of thin dentinal walls in the mesial root danger zone. Preservation of dentin in this region is therefore essential to reduce the risk of strip perforation and vertical root fracture.

The introduction of nickel-titanium (NiTi) rotary instruments has significantly improved the efficiency and predictability of root canal preparation. These instruments possess superior flexibility, shape memory, and resistance to cyclic fatigue compared to conventional stainless steel files. However, variations in instrument design—including taper, cross-sectional geometry, and metallurgical properties—result in differences in cutting efficiency and dentin removal patterns.

Recent advancements in rotary file systems have focused on the concept of minimally invasive endodontics. Systems such as TruNatomy are specifically engineered with reduced taper and a slim core to preserve dentin while maintaining effective canal shaping. In contrast, systems like ProTaper Gold, with progressive taper designs, may remove greater amounts of dentin despite offering efficient shaping. K3XF, utilizing R-phase heat-treated NiTi, represents an intermediate approach with enhanced flexibility and controlled cutting action.

Accurate evaluation of dentin thickness following instrumentation is essential for understanding the impact of different preparation techniques. Conventional radiographic methods are limited by their two-dimensional representation and inability to provide precise measurements. Micro-computed tomography, although highly accurate, is not always feasible due to cost and accessibility. Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT), on the other hand, offers a reliable, non-destructive, and three-dimensional imaging modality that allows precise assessment of dentin thickness with relatively lower radiation exposure.

Although several studies have evaluated the shaping ability of rotary systems, limited literature is available comparing the effect of contemporary minimally invasive systems such as TruNatomy, ProTaper Gold, and K3XF on pericervical dentin preservation with and without coronal flaring using CBCT analysis. Therefore, the present study was undertaken.

Given the clinical significance of preserving pericervical dentin and the variability among contemporary rotary systems, it becomes imperative to evaluate their effects on dentin thickness. Therefore, the present in vitro study was designed to assess and compare the remaining pericervical dentin thickness following instrumentation with different rotary file systems, with and without coronal flaring, using CBCT imaging.

However, limited evidence is available comparing the influence of TruNatomy, ProTaper Gold, and K3XF systems on pericervical dentin preservation under conditions with and without coronal flaring using CBCT analysis. Furthermore, comparative data regarding the combined effect of file design and coronal flaring on dentin conservation in mandibular molars remain insufficient.

To the best of our knowledge, very few studies have comparatively evaluated contemporary minimally invasive rotary systems with respect to pericervical dentin preservation using CBCT.

AIM & OBJECTIVES:

AIM:

To evaluate and compare the remaining pericervical dentin thickness after instrumentation with different rotary file systems, with and without coronal flaring, using CBCT.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To compare dentin thickness among TruNatomy, ProTaper Gold, and K3XF.
2. To evaluate the effect of coronal flaring on dentin preservation.
3. To assess dentin thickness at 1 mm, 2 mm, 3 mm, and 4 mm below furcation using CBCT.

NULL HYPOTHESIS:

There is no significant difference in remaining pericervical dentin thickness among the rotary file systems or between flaring and non-flaring groups.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design:

The present in vitro study was conducted to evaluate the remaining pericervical dentin thickness following instrumentation with different rotary file systems, with and without coronal flaring, using cone beam computed tomography (CBCT).

The methodology of the present in vitro study was designed and reported in accordance with the CRIS guidelines for laboratory studies.

The present study was designed and reported in accordance with the CRIS guidelines for in vitro studies.

Ethical Approval:

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of Rishiraj College of Dental Sciences and Research Centre, Bhopal.

Extracted teeth were collected after obtaining informed written consent from patients for the use of biological samples for research purposes.

Sample size Calculation:

Sample size was determined based on previous similar studies with a confidence interval of 95% and study power of 80%.

Samples were randomly allocated into groups using a computer-generated block randomization method.

Specimen Collection:

A total of 60 freshly extracted human mandibular first molars were collected from the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery. The teeth were extracted for periodontal or orthodontic reasons and were unrelated to this study.

Immediately after extraction, the teeth were cleaned of adherent soft tissue and calculus using ultrasonic scalers. The specimens were then rinsed under running water and stored in 10% buffered formalin solution until further use to prevent dehydration and maintain structural integrity.

Inclusion Criteria:

The following criteria were used for sample selection:

1. Extracted human mandibular first molars
2. Teeth with fully formed apices
3. Intact crowns and roots without fractures
4. Absence of caries, restorations, or previous endodontic treatment
5. Mesial roots with two distinct canals
6. Root curvature less than 20°, determined using Schneider’s method

Exclusion Criteria:

Teeth exhibiting any of the following were excluded:

1. Internal or external root resorption
2. Calcified or obliterated canals
3. Cracks or fractures in the root
4. Open apices
5. Severe root curvature greater than 20°
6. Developmental anomalies

Specimen Preparation:

The crowns of all selected teeth were sectioned at the cemento-enamel junction using a diamond disc under continuous water cooling to standardize root length. The mesial roots were then separated from the distal roots.

Working length was determined by introducing a size 10 K-file into the canal until the tip was visible at the apical foramen, and 1 mm was subtracted from this length.

Examiner Calibration and Blinding:

- All instrumentation procedures were performed by a single experienced operator to eliminate inter-operator variability.
- CBCT measurements were assessed by a blinded examiner who was unaware of group allocation.
- Ten randomly selected samples were re-evaluated after two weeks to assess intra-examiner reliability using Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC).

Mounting of Samples:

All specimens were embedded in self-cure acrylic resin blocks to ensure stability and standardization during instrumentation and CBCT scanning procedures.

Grouping of Samples:

The samples were randomly divided into two main groups (n = 30 each):

- **Group I:** Without coronal flaring
- **Group II:** With coronal flaring

Each group was further subdivided into three subgroups (n = 10 each):

- **Subgroup A:** TruNatomy
- **Subgroup B:** ProTaper Gold
- **Subgroup C:** K3XF

Instrumentation Protocol:

File System	Sequence Used	Final Apical Size	Taper
TruNatomy	Small, Prime	26	.04
ProTaper Gold	SX-S1-S2-F1-F2	25	Variable
K3XF	20/.04 to 25/.06	25	.06

Group I (Without Coronal Flaring):

Canal preparation was performed directly using the assigned rotary file system according to the manufacturer’s instructions.

Group II (With Coronal Flaring):

Coronal flaring was performed prior to canal instrumentation using Coronal flaring was performed using ProTaper SX files before rotary instrumentation. This was followed by canal preparation using the designated rotary file system as per manufacturer guidelines.

Irrigation Protocol:

Throughout the instrumentation procedure, canals were irrigated using:

- 3% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) as the primary irrigant
- 17% ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) as a final rinse
- Normal saline to flush debris
- A total of 2 mL of irrigant was used between each instrument change.

CBCT Evaluation:

Pre-Instrumentation Scan

All samples were subjected to CBCT scanning prior to instrumentation to record baseline dentin thickness.

Post-Instrumentation Scan

Following completion of canal preparation, the samples were rescanned under identical parameters.

Measurement of Dentin Thickness:

The remaining dentin thickness was measured at four levels:

- 1 mm below the furcation (D1)
- 2 mm below the furcation (D2)
- 3 mm below the furcation (D3)
- 4 mm below the furcation (D4)

Measurements were taken from the inner canal wall to the outer root surface, specifically focusing on the danger zone.

Statistical Analysis:

The collected data were analyzed using SPSS software.

- One-way ANOVA was used for intergroup comparisons
- Tukey post hoc test was used for pairwise comparisons
- Independent t-test was used to compare flaring and non-flaring groups

A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Table 1: Comparison of Mean Remaining Peri cervical Dentin Thickness (mm) Among Different File Systems at Various Levels (n=60)

Level	File System	N	Mean ± SD	F-value	p-value
1 mm (D1)	TruNatomy	20	1.337 ± 0.02	1097.0	0.001
	K3XF	20	1.187 ± 0.02		
	ProTaper	20	1.031 ± 0.01		
2 mm (D2)	TruNatomy	20	1.467± 0.02	1097.5	0.001
	K3XF	20	1.307 ± 0.02		
	ProTaper	20	1.161 ± 0.01		
3 mm (D3)	TruNatomy	20	1.592± 0.01	1510.0	0.001
	K3XF	20	1.4315± 0.01		
	ProTaper	20	1.286 ± 0.01		
4 mm (D4)	TruNatomy	20	1.712 ± 0.01	1508.8	0.001
	K3XF	20	1.561 ± 0.01		
	ProTaper	20	1.406 ± 0.01		

Figure 1: Comparison of Mean Remaining Peri cervical Dentin Thickness (mm) Among Different File Systems at Various Levels (n=60)

The mean remaining peri cervical dentin thickness increased from 1 mm to 4 mm in all groups. At 1 mm, TruNatomy (1.337 mm) showed the highest dentin thickness, followed by K3XF (1.187 mm) and ProTaper (1.031 mm). A similar pattern was observed at 2 mm (1.467, 1.307, 1.161 mm), 3 mm (1.592, 1.431, 1.286 mm), and 4 mm (1.712, 1.561, 1.406 mm), respectively.

At all levels, the differences among the file systems were highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that file system design significantly affects peri cervical dentin preservation. Overall, TruNatomy preserved the maximum dentin, whereas ProTaper showed the least preservation.

Table 2: Multiple Comparison of File Systems Using Tukey Post Hoc Test

Comparison	D1	D2	D3	D4
TruNatomy vs K3XF	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
TruNatomy vs ProTaper	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
K3XF vs ProTaper	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001

The Tukey post hoc analysis revealed that all pairwise comparisons between the file systems were statistically highly significant at all levels (D1–D4), with $p < 0.001$. Specifically, significant differences were observed between TruNatomy and K3XF, TruNatomy and ProTaper, and K3XF and ProTaper at each measurement level. This indicates that each file system exhibited a distinct effect on pericervical dentin preservation. Based on the mean values, TruNatomy consistently preserved the maximum dentin thickness, followed by K3XF, while ProTaper demonstrated the least preservation. These findings confirm that the choice of file system plays a crucial role in influencing dentin conservation in the peri cervical region.

Table 3: Comparison of Remaining Peri cervical Dentin Thickness (mm) Between Flaring and Non-Flaring Groups

Level	Group	N	Mean ± SD	t-value	p-value
D1 (1 mm)	No Flaring	30	1.198 ± 0.11	0.782	0.434
	Flaring	30	1.172 ± 0.12		
D2 (2 mm)	No Flaring	30	1.325 ± 0.10	0.781	0.434
	Flaring	30	1.299 ± 0.13		
D3 (3 mm)	No Flaring	30	1.446 ± 0.12	0.568	0.574
	Flaring	30	1.427 ± 0.10		
D4 (4 mm)	No Flaring	30	1.569 ± 0.11	0.567	0.573
	Flaring	30	1.550 ± 0.12		

Figure 2: Comparison of Remaining Peri cervical Dentin Thickness (mm) Between Flaring and Non-Flaring Groups

The independent sample t-test showed that the mean remaining peri cervical dentin thickness was slightly higher in the non-flaring group compared to the flaring group at all levels. At 1 mm, the mean values were 1.198 mm (no flaring) and 1.172 mm (flaring) ($p = 0.434$). Similarly, at 2 mm, the values were 1.325 mm and 1.299 mm ($p = 0.434$), at 3 mm, 1.446 mm and 1.427 mm ($p = 0.574$), and at 4 mm, 1.569 mm and 1.550 mm ($p = 0.573$), respectively. However, these differences were not statistically significant at any level ($p > 0.05$). This indicates that the use of coronal flaring did not significantly influence peri cervical dentin thickness.

Table 4: Combined Effect of File System and Coronal Flaring on Remaining Peri cervical Dentin Thickness at 1 mm (D1)

File System	No Flaring (Mean ± SD)	Flaring (Mean ± SD)	Total (Mean ± SD)	F-value	p-value
TruNatomy	1.350 ± 0.01	1.324 ± 0.01	1.337 ± 0.02		
K3XF	1.200 ± 0.01	1.175 ± 0.01	1.187 ± 0.02		
ProTaper	1.045 ± 0.01	1.018 ± 0.01	1.03 ± 0.01		
Overall (Group Effect)	1.198 ± 0.12	1.1723 ± 0.12	—	38.834	0.001

File Effect	—	—	—	1787.44	0.001
File × Group Interaction	—	—	—	0.019	0.981

Figure 3: Combined Effect of File System and Coronal Flaring on Remaining Peri cervical Dentin Thickness at 1 mm (D1)

At the 1 mm level (D1), TruNatomy showed the highest mean remaining pericervical dentin thickness in both non-flaring (1.3500 mm) and flaring groups (1.3240 mm), followed by K3XF (1.2000 mm and 1.1750 mm) and ProTaper (1.0450 mm and 1.0180 mm). Two-way ANOVA revealed a highly significant effect of the file system ($F = 1787.445$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the type of file significantly influences dentin preservation. Although the group effect (flaring vs non-flaring) was also statistically significant ($F = 38.834$, $p < 0.001$), the actual difference in mean values was minimal. The interaction between file system and flaring was not statistically significant ($F = 0.019$, $p = 0.981$), suggesting that the effect of flaring was consistent across all file systems.

Table 5: Combined Effect of File System and Coronal Flaring on Remaining Pericervical Dentin Thickness at 2 mm (D2)

File System	No Flaring (Mean ± SD)	Flaring (Mean ± SD)	Total (Mean ± SD)	F-value	p-value
TruNatomy	1.480 ± 0.01	1.454 ± 0.01	1.467 ± 0.02		
K3XF	1.3200 ± 0.01	1.295 ± 0.01	1.307 ± 0.02		
ProTaper	1.175 ± 0.01	1.148 ± 0.01	1.161 ± 0.01		
Overall (Group Effect)	1.325 ± 0.12	1.299 ± 0.12	—	38.834	0.001
File Effect	—	—	—	1788.3	0.001
File × Group Interaction	—	—	—	0.019	0.981

Figure 4: Combined Effect of File System and Coronal Flaring on Remaining Pericervical Dentin Thickness at 2 mm (D2)

At the 2 mm level (D2), TruNatomy demonstrated the highest mean remaining pericervical dentin thickness in both non-flaring (1.4800 mm) and flaring groups (1.4540 mm), followed by K3XF (1.3200 mm and 1.2950 mm) and ProTaper (1.1750 mm and 1.1480 mm). Two-way ANOVA showed a highly significant effect of the file system ($F = 1788.338$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the choice of file system significantly affects dentin preservation. The group effect (flaring vs non-flaring) was also statistically significant ($F = 38.834$, $p < 0.001$), although the actual difference in mean values was minimal. The interaction between file system and flaring was not statistically significant ($F = 0.019$, $p = 0.981$), suggesting that the influence of coronal flaring was consistent across all file systems.

Table 6: Combined Effect of File System and Coronal Flaring on Remaining Pericervical Dentin Thickness at 3 mm (D3)

File System	No Flaring (Mean ± SD)	Flaring (Mean ± SD)	Total (Mean ± SD)	F-value	p-value
TruNatomy	1.600 ± 0.018	1.584 ± 0.015	1.592 ± 0.01		
K3XF	1.443 ± 0.014	1.420 ± 0.012	1.431 ± 0.01		
ProTaper	1.295 ± 0.015	1.278 ± 0.013	1.286 ± 0.016		
Overall (Group Effect)	1.446 ± 0.127	1.427 ± 0.127	—	23.021	0.001
File Effect	—	—	—	2057.16	0.001
File × Group Interaction	—	—	—	0.316	0.731

At the 3 mm level (D3), TruNatomy showed the highest mean remaining peri cervical dentin thickness in both non-flaring (1.6000 mm) and flaring groups (1.5840 mm), followed by K3XF (1.4430 mm and 1.4200 mm) and ProTaper (1.2950 mm and 1.2780 mm). Two-way ANOVA demonstrated a highly significant effect of the file system ($F = 2057.161$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that file design plays a major role in dentin preservation. The group effect (flaring vs non-flaring) was also statistically significant ($F = 23.021$, $p < 0.001$), although the actual differences in mean values were small. The interaction between file system and flaring was not statistically significant ($F = 0.316$, $p = 0.731$), suggesting that the effect of coronal flaring was similar across all file systems.

Table 7: Combined Effect of File System and Coronal Flaring on Remaining Pericervical Dentin Thickness at 4 mm (D4)

File System	No Flaring (Mean ± SD)	Flaring (Mean ± SD)	Total (Mean ± SD)	F-value	p-value
TruNatomy	1.720 ± 0.01	1.704 ± 0.01	1.712 ± 0.018		
K3XF	1.573 ± 0.01	1.55 ± 0.01	1.561 ± 0.017		
ProTaper	1.415 ± 0.01	1.398 ± 0.01	1.406 ± 0.016		
Overall (Group Effect)	1.569 ± 0.12	1.550 ± 0.127	—	23.021	0.001
File Effect	—	—	—	2055.54	0.001
File × Group Interaction	—	—	—	0.316	0.731

At the 4 mm level (D4), TruNatomy demonstrated the highest mean remaining pericervical dentin thickness in both non-flaring (1.7200 mm) and flaring groups (1.7040 mm), followed by K3XF (1.5730 mm and 1.5500 mm) and ProTaper (1.4150 mm and 1.3980 mm). Two-way ANOVA revealed a highly significant effect of the file system ($F = 2055.546$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the type of file system significantly influences dentin preservation. The group effect (flaring vs non-flaring) was also statistically significant ($F = 23.021$, $p < 0.001$), although the differences in mean values were minimal. The interaction between file system and flaring was not statistically significant ($F = 0.316$, $p = 0.731$), suggesting that the influence of coronal flaring was consistent across all file systems.

Summary of Results

- Dentin thickness increased from 1 mm to 4 mm in all groups, showing natural increase toward apical region.
- At all levels (D1–D4), TruNatomy showed the highest remaining dentin thickness, followed by K3XF, while ProTaper showed the least.
- One-way ANOVA showed highly significant differences among file systems at all levels ($p < 0.001$).
- Tukey post hoc test confirmed that all pairwise comparisons (TruNatomy vs K3XF, TruNatomy vs ProTaper, K3XF vs ProTaper) were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).
- Independent t-test showed no significant difference between flaring and non-flaring groups at any level ($p > 0.05$).
- Although mean dentin thickness was slightly higher in the non-flaring group, the difference was not statistically significant.
- Two-way ANOVA showed:
 - Significant file system effect ($p < 0.001$)
 - Significant group effect ($p < 0.001$) (statistically, but clinically minimal)

- No significant interaction between file system and flaring ($p > 0.05$)
- The effect of flaring was consistent across all file systems, meaning no file was affected differently by flaring.
 - Overall, file design had a greater impact on dentin preservation than coronal flaring.
 - Final order of dentin preservation: TruNatomy > K3XF > ProTaper

DISCUSSION:

The present study evaluated the effect of different rotary file systems, with and without coronal flaring, on remaining pericervical dentin thickness using CBCT. Preservation of dentin in the pericervical region is critical, as it plays a vital role in maintaining the structural integrity and fracture resistance of endodontically treated teeth.

The present findings are consistent with previous studies that emphasized the importance of conservative instrumentation in preserving structural dentin.

The results demonstrated that TruNatomy preserved the maximum dentin thickness at all levels, followed by K3XF and ProTaper, with statistically significant

differences ($p < 0.001$). The superior performance of TruNatomy can be attributed to its conservative design, characterized by reduced taper and enhanced flexibility, allowing it to maintain canal anatomy while minimizing dentin removal.

ProTaper showed the least remaining dentin thickness, likely due to its progressive taper and higher cutting efficiency, which may lead to greater dentin removal in the cervical region. K3XF exhibited intermediate results, reflecting a balance between flexibility and cutting action. A gradual increase in dentin thickness from coronal to apical levels was observed across all groups, indicating that the pericervical region is the most susceptible to dentin loss during instrumentation. This highlights the importance of adopting conservative preparation techniques in this critical zone.

Coronal flaring resulted in slightly lower dentin thickness values; however, the differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that controlled flaring does not significantly compromise dentin preservation and can be safely performed to improve access and irrigation.

The use of CBCT enabled accurate three-dimensional evaluation of dentin thickness, providing reliable assessment of structural changes following instrumentation. However, as an in vitro study, clinical conditions such as functional loading and periodontal support were not replicated.

Within these limitations, the findings emphasize that rotary file system selection plays a significant role in dentin preservation, supporting the principles of minimally invasive endodontics.

Further clinical studies with larger sample sizes and long-term fracture resistance evaluation are recommended to validate the present findings.

LIMITATIONS:

1. Being an in vitro study, clinical conditions could not be completely simulated.
2. Functional occlusal loading was not evaluated.
3. Long-term fracture resistance was not assessed.
4. Limited sample size.
5. Thermocycling and periodontal ligament simulation were not performed.
6. Only mandibular first molars were evaluated.
7. Micro-CT comparison was not performed.

Clinical Relevance:

Preservation of pericervical dentin may improve fracture resistance and longevity of endodontically treated teeth. Conservative rotary systems may therefore be preferred in minimally invasive endodontic procedures.

CONCLUSION:

Within the limitations of this in vitro CBCT study, it can be inferred that the type of file system significantly influences the preservation of peri cervical dentin in mandibular molars. Among the systems evaluated, TruNatomy demonstrated the highest dentin preservation, followed by K3XF, while ProTaper showed the least preservation at all levels (1–4 mm).

Although coronal flaring resulted in a slight reduction in dentin thickness, the difference between flaring and non-flaring groups was not statistically significant, indicating that coronal flaring has minimal clinical impact on pericervical dentin preservation.

Furthermore, no significant interaction was observed between file system and flaring, suggesting that the effect of flaring is consistent across different file systems.

Overall, file design plays a more critical role than coronal flaring in preserving pericervical dentin, with conservative file systems like TruNatomy being more favorable for maintaining tooth structure.

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Author Contributions:

Dr. Madhulika Banerjee: Conceptualization, methodology, data collection, manuscript preparation.

Dr. Indra Gupta: Statistical analysis and interpretation.

Dr. Vaishnavi Laychettiwari: CBCT evaluation and data acquisition.

Dr. Dipali Kumari: Literature review and manuscript editing.

Data Availability Statement:

The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Informed Consent:

Informed consent was obtained from all patients prior to extraction and use of teeth for research purposes.

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